

Research Article

Turbine and Generator are placed on a certain height in Thermal Power Plants- A Cooling Tower case study

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Abstract: This paper presents that the cooling towers are the most valuable equipment in industries usually to dissipate residual process heat loads at a very reasonable cost. Apart from providing inexpensive and excellent heat transfer media they play an essential role to lower the heat rate or increase the efficiency of the complex within certain temperature limits. As world's population & industry is growing day by day energy conservation has become as necessary as other super essential priorities. Hence Cooling Towers are designed to conserve & re-use water intakes through recirculation in order to remove process heat with minimum water losses.

Keywords: Cooling tower, saturated steam, super-heated steam, steam turbine

1. Introduction

A cooling tower is a specialized heat exchanger in which air and water are brought into direct contact with each other in order to reduce the water's temperature. As this occurs, a small volume of water is evaporated, reducing the temperature of the water being circulated through the tower. Water, which has been heated by an industrial process or in an air-conditioning condenser, is pumped to the cooling tower through pipes [1-2]. The water sprays through nozzles onto banks of material called "fill," which slows the flow of water through the cooling tower, and exposes as much water surface area as possible for maximum air-water contact. As the water flows through the cooling tower, it is exposed to air, which is being pulled through the tower by the electric motor-driven fan [3]. When the water and air meet, a small amount of water is evaporated, creating a cooling action. The cooled water is then pumped back to the condenser or

process equipment where it absorbs heat. It will then be come back to the cooling tower to be cooled once again. Cooling Tower Fundamentals provides a level of basic cooling tower knowledge and is a great resource for those wanting to learn more [4]. Not all towers are suitable for all applications. Cooling towers are designed and manufactured in several types, with numerous sizes available. Understanding the various types, along with their advantages and limitations, is important when determining the right tower for a project. The product list provides an overview of towers to help you determine which is right for your application. In cross flow towers the water flows vertically through the fill while the air flows horizontally, across the flow of the falling water. Because of this, air does not have to pass through the distribution system, permitting the use of gravity flow hot water distribution basins mounted at the top of the unit above the fill [5]. These basins are universally applied on all cross flow towers. Counter flow towers are designed so that air flows vertically upward, counter to the flow of falling water in the fill. Because of this vertical airflow, it is not possible to use the open, gravity-flow basins typical in cross flow designs. Instead, counter flow towers use pressurized, pipe-type spray systems to spray water onto the top of the fill. Since air must be able to pass through the spray system, the pipes and nozzles must be farther apart so as not to restrict airflow. Induced draft cooling towers have fans that are typically mounted on top of the unit and pull air through the fill media. Conversely, air is pushed by blowers located at the base of the air inlet face on forced draft towers. Factory-assembled towers (FAP) are built and shipped in as few sections as the mode of transportation will permit. A relatively small tower will ship essentially intact. A larger, multi-cell cooling tower is manufactured as modules at the factory, and shipped ready for final assembly. Factory-assembled towers are also known as “packaged” or “FAP” (factory-assembled product). Factory-assembled cooling towers can be cross flow or counterflow, induced draft or forced draft, depending on the application [6]. While all applications are different, the factory-assembled Marley NC cross flow, induced draft tower is widely used for HVAC and light industrial applications. Field-erected cooling towers (FEP) Field-erected towers are primarily constructed at the site of ultimate use. All large cooling towers, and many of the smaller towers, are prefabricated, piece-marked, and shipped to the site for final assembly. The manufacturer usually provides labor and supervision for final assembly [7-8]. Field-erected towers can be cross flow or counter flow, depending on the application. For power and heavy industrial applications, the field-erected Marley F400 counterblow tower can be customized to meet your exact

specifications for performance, structure, drift and plume abatement. Using a total system approach, every cooling tower and component is designed and engineered to work together as an integrated system for efficient performance and long life [9]. HVAC Free Cooling – A free cooling system allows the tower to directly satisfy a building’s cooling needs without the need of operating the chiller in cold weather. The goal of a free cooling system is to save energy. There are specific types of free cooling systems and certain elements that must be in place for a free cooling system to be considered [10]. Variable Flow – There may be significant energy savings opportunities if the cooling tower can be operated under variable flow in off-peak conditions. Variable flow is a way to maximize the effectiveness of the installed tower capacity for whatever flow the process has. Learnt more about SPX Variable Flow from literature review [11].

2. Methodology and experimental setup:

Their working principle is based on temperature gradient. Cooling water is supplied to the system, hot water comes back and after encounter with ambient temperature and air as media exchanges its heat and collected as cooling water in reservoir to be pumped back to the system and this cycle goes on. Exposure of hot water causes convection, conduction and radiation heat transfer processes due to which evaporation is achieved and evaporation causes cooling. Moreover these are two types of heats that cause heat transfer, 1 Sensible Heat owing to the difference in temperatures of water and air. 2 Latent Heat owing to the vaporization of small amount of water, Heat transfer rate for cooling tower is given as below;

$$Q=UA\Delta T \quad (\text{BTU/Hr})$$

Whereas;

Q= Rate of heat transfer

A= Surface area

DT= Log mean temperature difference (LMTD).

Efficiency of Cooling Tower is given as;

$$E= ((C_{Wi} - C_{Wo}) / (C_{Wi} - \text{Wet Bulb temperature})) * 100$$

Whereas;

E= Efficiency

C_{Wi}= Cooling Tower inlet water temperature

C_{Wo}= Cooling Tower outlet water temperature

And Wet Bulb temperature is the minimum achievable temperature in that specific atmospheric condition, Also;

$$E = (\text{Range} / (\text{Range} + \text{Approach})) * 100$$

Range is the difference between cooling tower inlet water temperature and cooling tower outlet water temperature. Approach is the difference between the cooling tower outlet water temperature and Wet Bulb temperature.

But as most of the Thermal Power Plants are based on 3R (Regenerative, Reheat, Rankine) Cycle, so that the cooling tower efficiency is controlled and depends on cycle design limits and constraints. While designing the thermal height of the turbine which is that specific height where turbine is placed above the ground coupled with Generator cooling water plays an essential role. These Turbines are multistage, condensing type with large multi-step heavy shafts. Their final stage is called Low Pressure or LP stage from where steam comes to the condenser through exhaust hood after doing mechanical work. To re-use such an expensive, chemically treated and demineralized water it is condensed into the condenser by the help of cooling water. Inside LP stage of the turbine some blades are called sacrificial blades because they have to bear maximum tip velocity caused by the driving Pressure/vacuum which is generated due to the condensation and it's pulling effect.

The driving Pressure is given as;

$$PD = (\rho_o - \rho_i) * g * H$$

Whereas;

ρ_o = density of LP turbine outlet steam

ρ_i = density of LP turbine inlet steam

g = gravitational acceleration/pull

H = Height of the turbine above the ground

As 1 unit volume of water when converted to superheated steam occupies space of 1600 unit volume of water so when it is converted back to water at condensation point inside the condenser leaves space of 1599 unit volume of water which is actually the vacuum. Condensate is reclaimed from the condenser through pumps the cycle goes on and continued. The Approach is the difference between the cooling tower outlet water temperature and Wet Bulb temperature in the cooling peripheral which creates pressure inside of the cooling materials throughout the cycle in the system.

3. Results and Discussion

If vacuum inside the condenser increases the condensation point rises above from the condenser normal operating water level (Hot well level). Condensation point is the area inside the condenser where phase change occurs and steam starts converting to liquid. It causes more driving pressure and more tip velocity is experienced by the LP turbine sacrificial stages. It is necessary to prevent any liquefaction inside LP stage of turbine because water droplets will hit the blades like bullets, because pitting and large vibrations are experienced along the bearings of the turbine. In severe cases if turbine doesn't trip due to high vibrations, condenser high level or other protections it can damage the equipment on a large scale. To prevent this height of the turbine should be increased as in adiabatically isolated system if pressure (g) decreases the boiling point of the water also decreases that means condensations becomes difficult. Hence higher the turbine, lower the condensation point. Figure 1 shows the condenser alignment with steam levels for the experimental setup throughout our study.

Figure 1 Condenser alignment with steam levels

Condensation inside the condenser is because of cooling tower and more than 90% of the vacuum is generated due to this phenomenon so all the responsibility to controls the vacuum lies on cooling tower. Although more low temperature of the cooling water and eventually more vacuum improve the overall efficiency/heat rate of the complex but due to design limitations it is not favorable for vacuum to go beyond upper or lower limits. 17.5m and 8.5m are the worldwide

proposed thermal heights due to constraints/limitations of the strength of supporting structure. The cooling tower operates efficiently at the thermal power plant here in our study the intake water temperature was determined $CW_i = 41$ °C and when the water comes out of the cooling tower outlet it gets colder and the temperature drops around $CW_o = 31$ °C. Similarly, the temperature of the wet bulb is recorded 27 °C throughout this experimental period. The Range of cooling tower used in this study was kept constant about 10 °C for the cooling process with 4 °C approach. The 720 mmH₂O vacuum was created in the condenser. The generator and steam turbine played a very important role throughout this process. The height of the steam turbine was kept 8.5m in the whole process.

Natural draught cooling towers utilize buoyancy via a tall hyperboloid chimney. Hyperboloid cooling towers are typical for natural draught cooling towers because of their structural strength and because of the fact that the hyperboloid shape also aids in accelerating the upward convective air flow, improving cooling efficiency. In this cooling tower the hot cooling water (e.g. 25°C) from the condenser is pumped to a height of about 10 m, enters the tower and then sprayed over the trays. Water droplets fall down and meet the colder air entering from the bottom of the tower which is open to the atmosphere. Hot water (e.g. 25°C) gives up its heat to the air and gets cooled (e.g. 22°C). Warm, moist air naturally rises due to the density differential compared to the dry, cooler outside air. Warm moist air is less dense than drier air at the same pressure. This moist air buoyancy produces an upwards current of air through the hyperboloid tower. The cooled water falls down in the form of rain and gets collected in the pond at the bottom of the tower. An increase in the ambient temperature may cause a proportional increase in pressure of exhausted steam ($\Delta T = 14^\circ\text{C}$ is usually a constant) hence the thermal efficiency of the power conversion system may decrease. In other words, the electrical output of a power plant may vary with ambient conditions, while the thermal power remains constant. It must be noted there is also lower limit for the steam outlet temperature, thus for the cooling system. Below 0.008 MPa and 41.5 °C the specific volume of exhausted steam significantly increases which requires huge blades in last rows of low-pressure stage of the steam turbine. Moreover, with a decrease in the turbine exhaust pressure the vapor quality decreases (or dryness fraction). At some point the expansion must be ended to avoid damages that could be caused to blades of steam turbine by low quality steam. In modern nuclear power plants the overall thermal efficiency is about one-third (33%), so 3000 MW of thermal power from the fission reaction is

needed to generate 1000 MW of electrical power. Therefore about 2000MWth of unusable energy must be rejected in order to fulfill the second law of thermodynamics. To maintain the parameters inside the condenser (0.008 MPa and 41.5 °C), the cooling water must be sufficiently cold and there cannot be large temperature difference between the outlet and inlet water temperature, hence the flow rate through the cooling system must be very high.

4. Conclusion

This study describes that once the height of the cooling tower has been designed, the turbo generator well-ordered and installed in the workplace, then the vacuum control phenomena end up through the cooling tower. Either the cooling tower cells are changed throughout the process according to the load variations or the installation of the drive at variable speeds as the main cooling tower drives are favorable to the fans. Mainly for accurate control of vacuum cooling towers fans are driven by induction motors with variable frequency devices. Cooling tower analysis for each thermal power plant is very useful to determine the performance and efficiency. In this study it is estimated that if the induction fan is used, then the efficiency of the cooling tower gradually increases while maintaining some stable long parameters in working conditions.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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